

Some Anionic Organotellurium Complexes

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Complexes of the formulae $[R_4N]_2^+[C_6H_{10}TeI_2X'_2]^{2-}$ and $[R_4N]^+[p-C_6H_4-OC_6H_4TeCl_2X']^-$, where $R=CH_3, C_2H_5, C_6H_7$ or C_6H_9 ; $X'=I, Br$ or Cl , have been synthesised by refluxing a solution of 1-telluracyclohexane 1:1 diiodide or *p*-phenoxyphenyltellurium trichloride in chloroform with tetraalkylammonium halides in the same solvent. The complexes are ionic in nature and have been characterised through analytical, conductance and molecular weight data and nmr spectral studies. The activity of the complexes against certain microorganisms has been tested but not found significant.

COMPLEXES containing dihalo- or tetrahalomono-organotellurate anions of the formula $[R_4N]_2^+[C_6H_{10}TeI_2X'_2]^{2-}$ and $[R_4N]^+[p-C_6H_4-OC_6H_4TeCl_2X']^-$ have recently been reported¹⁻⁴. In continuation of our studies on Lewis acid behaviour of diorganotellurium dihalides^{5,6} we report the synthesis, characterization and antimicrobial activity of some new complexes of the formulae $[R_4N]_2^+[C_6H_{10}TeI_2X'_2]^{2-}$ and $[R_4N]^+[p-C_6H_4-OC_6H_4TeCl_2X']^-$.

Experimental

1-Telluracyclohexane-1,1-diiodide⁷ and *p*-phenoxyphenyltellurium trichloride⁸ were prepared by reported methods. Tetraalkylammonium halides were obtained from B.D.H. and used as such. ¹H NMR, molecular weight and conductivity data were collected as reported earlier⁵.

The desired complexes were prepared (a) by the direct interaction of tetraalkylammonium halides with organotellurium halides and (b) by halogen exchange reaction in certain organotellurium(IV) tetrahalo anions.

(a) 1-Telluracyclohexane-1,1-diiodide (2 m mol) was refluxed with a solution of tetraalkylammonium salt (4 m mol) in chloroform or dichloromethane (50 ml) for 4-5 hr. Concentration of the reaction mixture followed by addition of petroleum ether (40-60°) afforded the desired complexes which were recrystallised from dichloromethane/petroleum ether (40-60°) mixture.

(b) An aqueous solution of potassium iodide (4 m mol) was added to a solution of tetramethylammoniumtrichlorobromo-*p*-phenoxyphenyltellurate(IV) (0.55 g; 1 m mol) in 4 N HCl with constant stirring. The corresponding tetraiodo compound was precipitated in quantitative yield, filtered, washed with water and air dried.

Analytical data of the complexes prepared are given in Tables 1 and 2.

Results and Discussion

All the complexes are crystalline solids with sharp melting points. Molar conductance values of 10⁻³M solution in acetonitrile lie in the range 208-250 ohm⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹ for tetrahalocyclohexanetellurates and 124-168 ohm⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹ for tetrahalo-*p*-phenoxyphenyltellurates. The values correspond to 2:1 and 1:1 electrolytic behaviour of the complexes, respectively⁹. The observed molecular weights (in nitrobenzene) for tetrahalocyclohexanetellurates are approximately one-third of the calculated value indicating that the complexes are dissociated into three ions in solution, whereas the observed molecular weights of tetrahalo-*p*-phenoxyphenyltellurates are about half of the calculated values showing their 1:1 electrolytic behaviour.

Infrared spectra: Infrared spectra of the complexes have been recorded in the region 4000-400 cm⁻¹. Vibrational frequencies associated with the cations are in close agreement with those reported¹⁰ and are not tabulated. Infrared absorption associated with $\nu(Te-C)$ lies in the range 530 ± 10 cm⁻¹ and is not significantly affected by the nature of the halide groups attached to the metal atom.

¹H NMR: ¹H NMR spectra of $[(C_2H_5)_4N]_2^+[C_6H_{10}TeI_2Br_2]^{2-}$ and $[(C_2H_5)_4N]^+[p-C_6H_4-OC_6H_4TeCl_4]^-$ were recorded at room temperature. A multiplet in the region δ 3.34- δ 3.12 is observed due to CH₂-N protons whereas a triplet in the region δ 1.27- δ 1.21 may be assigned to -CH₂ protons. Two multiplets at δ 3.34 (coupled with the singlet at δ 2.35 to -CH₂-Te and CH₂-N protons) are attributed to -CH₂-Te and telluracyclohexane derivatives¹¹. Two doublets at δ 7.90 and δ 6.51 are observed due to *m*- and *o*- protons of aromatic ring bonded to tellurium in *p*-phenoxyphenyl derivative¹². A complex at δ 6.90 may be assigned to phenyl ring (C₆H₅O-) in

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF $[R_4N]_2[C_6H_5OC_6H_4TeI_2X']_2$

R	X'	m.p. °C	Yield %	Colour	Analysis%, Found (Calcd.)					Conductance ohm ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹ cm ²	Molecular weight, Found (Calcd.)
					Te	C	H	N	X'		
Me	Cl	230	70	White	19.00 (19.04)	23.25 (23.31)	5.01 (5.11)	4.15 (4.18)	48.09 (48.48)	208	215.2 (669.8)
Me	Br	190d	75	Greenish	16.56 (16.79)	20.50 (20.55)	4.55 (4.51)	3.50 (3.68)	54.16 (54.44)	235	240.2 (759.6)
Me	I	128	76	Purple	14.75 (14.94)	18.15 (18.28)	4.00 (4.01)	3.22 (3.28)	59.40 (59.50)	220	415.5 (853.6)
Et	Cl	120	85	Brown	15.90 (16.29)	32.10 (32.21)	6.35 (6.43)	3.55 (3.57)	41.30 (41.47)	210	250.0 (783.0)
Et	Br	175	79	Yellow	14.55 (14.63)	28.80 (28.93)	5.50 (5.78)	3.15 (3.21)	47.02 (47.43)	239	280.6 (871.8)
Et	I	194	72	Brown	13.00 (13.21)	25.99 (26.11)	5.15 (5.21)	2.88 (2.90)	52.50 (52.55)	212	324.8 (965.8)
Pr	I	139-141	80	Brown	10.95 (11.93)	32.00 (32.30)	6.15 (6.17)	2.56 (2.59)	47.00 (47.08)	210	359.3 (1078.9)
Bu	Cl	110	80	Brown	12.50 (12.66)	44.10 (44.11)	8.10 (8.20)	2.70 (2.78)	31.90 (32.28)	250	320.8 (1007.4)
Bu	I	122	68	Brown	10.52 (10.72)	37.20 (37.33)	6.92 (6.94)	2.30 (2.35)	42.16 (42.64)	240	350.0 (1190.0)
*Et	I	194	75	Dark brown	13.15 (13.21)	25.95 (26.11)	5.20 (5.21)	2.80 (2.90)	52.45 (52.55)	210	315.5 (965.8)

 TABLE 2—ANALYTICAL DATA OF $[R_4N][p-C_6H_4OC_6H_4TeCl_2X']$

R	X'	m.p. °C	Yield %	Colour	Analysis%, Found (Calcd.)					Conductance ohm ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹ cm ²	Molecular weight, Found (Calcd.)
					Te	C	H	N	X'		
Me	Cl	230	70	White	24.56 (24.87)	37.75 (37.46)	4.10 (4.12)	2.68 (2.73)	27.63 (27.73)	140	240.4 (512.9)
Me	Br	172	85	Light yellow	22.70 (22.89)	34.30 (34.47)	3.70 (3.79)	2.45 (2.51)	32.86 (33.44)	151	260.6 (557.3)
Me	I	196	89	Brown	20.95 (21.11)	31.60 (31.79)	3.45 (3.50)	2.29 (2.31)	38.55 (38.63)	150	302.1 (604.3)
Et	Cl	116	80	White	21.90 (22.40)	42.15 (42.21)	5.12 (5.13)	2.42 (2.46)	24.80 (24.95)	124	280.5 (569.4)
Et	Br	113-115	89	Light yellow	20.59 (20.80)	38.96 (39.15)	4.68 (4.76)	2.25 (2.28)	30.25 (30.38)	142	290.2 (613.4)
Et	I	105	81	Brown	19.23 (19.32)	36.27 (36.37)	4.40 (4.42)	2.10 (2.12)	34.90 (35.18)	150	320.2 (660.4)
Pr	I	111-114	90	Brown	17.70 (17.81)	40.20 (40.23)	5.15 (5.20)	1.90 (1.95)	32.40 (32.58)	152	345.2 (716.3)
Bu	I	84	85	Purple	16.45 (16.51)	42.50 (43.52)	5.70 (5.87)	1.75 (1.81)	30.15 (30.22)	142	215.2 (772.6)
*Me	I	159	82	Reddish brown	14.40 (14.53)	21.70 (21.87)	2.30 (2.40)	1.49 (1.59)	57.67 (57.77)	155	430.0 (878.0)
*Et	I	116-117	92	Reddish brown	13.54 (13.66)	25.52 (25.70)	3.10 (3.12)	1.40 (1.49)	53.95 (54.30)	168	467.0 (934.0)

* Anionic complexes obtained by halogen exchange reaction.

$[(C_2H_5)_4N][C_6H_5OC_6H_4TeCl_2]$. The spectra and their integrations correspond to the proposed stoichiometry of the complexes. An octahedral and a square pyramidal structure are tentatively assigned to tetrahalocyclohexanetellurates and *p*-phenoxyphenyltetrahalotellurates, respectively in analogy with previous reports⁵⁻⁶.

Bio-assay: The antimicrobial activity of the complexes were screened against five bacteria *Streptococcus faecalis*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, and five fungi *Candida albicans*, *Cryptococcus neoformans*, *Sporotrichum schenikii*, *Trichophyton mentagrophytes*, *Aspergillus fumigatus*.

The complexes show moderate activity towards the bacteria and are inactive against the fungi.

The activity of the complexes (soluble in methanol) was assayed by twofold serial dilution method. The maximum concentration for the tested compound was 100 µg/ml. The fungi was incubated at 28 ± 1° and the bacteria at 37°. The incubation period was 24 hr for all the bacteria and the fungi *Candida albicans*, *Sporotrichum schenikii*, 48 hr for *Cryptococcus neoformans* and *Aspergillus fumigatus* and 96 hr for *Trichophyton mentagrophytes*. *Klebsiella pneumoniae* is affected by all the complexes. *Staphylococcus aureus* (gram positive) appears to be sensitive against bis-tetraethyl ammo-

nium tetraiodocyclohexanetellurate. *Bis-tetramethyl ammonium tetraiodocyclohexanetellurate* is active against *Streptococcus faecalis*. All the complexes are completely inactive against gram negative bacteria, *E. coli* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and all the fungi used.

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